

Figure 6, Panel F, date of file 06/05/2009

Enlarged section of interest

Figure 7, panel B, date of file 05/14/2008

Enlarged section of interest

Figure 5, bottom panel A, date of file 11/11/2010

Enlarged section of interest

Autoradiogram leading to Figure 5, Panel A, filed 05/26/2008

Autoradiogram leading to Figure 5, Panel A, filed 05/26/2008

Enlarged section of interest

Sections of interest

strongly darker by tonal correction:
0_0.32_255

Fig 5A, top panel, date of file 05/26/2008

Figure 7D, date of autoradiogram file 07/04/2009

Figure 7D, date of file 07/04/2009

Area (blue line) in lanes reflecting non-specific binding of many nuclear proteins to the radio-labeled oligo probe as well as unbound oligo

Enlarged section of interest

Figures 3A, date of file 03/17/2008

Enlarged section of interest

darker exposures

Figures 3A, date of file 03/17/2008

Enlarged section of interest

darker exposure

